

SCOPING PAPER

FLEXIBILITY

A NEFI Innovation Hub

NEFI – The Innovation Network for Industrial Transformation

NEFI – New Energy for Industry is an innovation network consisting of over 100 industry partners, 8 research partners, and 4 institutional partners. With 25 research and innovation projects dedicated to industrial transformation in Austria, an investment volume of nearly €100 million has been mobilised.

The goals of NEFI are:

- **Climate Neutrality** – Supplying selected sites with up to 100% renewable energy.
- **Value Creation and Location Security** – Promoting technology development and exports “Made in Austria”.
- **Industrial Resilience** – Ensuring energy supply, optimising processes, and improving infrastructure for Austrian industry.

The solutions developed within NEFI address 53% of the CO₂ emissions expected by 2040 and have the potential to generate an economic benefit of €2.2 billion. Additionally, by 2040, more than 25% of fossil energy imports could be avoided.

Achieving a climate-neutral industry by 2040 requires significant research and development efforts. Essential technologies are not yet fully developed, tested, or scalable to a sufficient extent. To bridge technological gaps and strategically drive innovations along realistic, scenario-based transformation pathways, six Innovation Hubs have been established.

NEFI Innovation Hubs

The NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. Their goal is to initiate high-impact research and innovation projects that support the transition to a climate-neutral industry and position Austria as a technology leader in renewable energy and industrial innovation.

Both large corporations and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), as well as research institutions, are invited to participate in the Innovation Hubs.

NEFI Innovation Hubs: value proposition for partners

- ☑ Regular networking and information events: The NEFI Technology Talks present current technologies, trends, and developments.
- ☑ Support throughout the innovation process: From project idea to funding application and impact assessment.
- ☑ Dissemination of results: Effective communication and visibility.
- ☑ Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure.

The NEFI Innovation Hubs focus on the following key areas: CCUS, Circular Economy, CO₂-neutral Gases & Hydrogen, Electrification & Energy Efficiency, Flexibility, and Industrial Symbiosis. These topics have been identified as crucial for achieving industrial climate goals across different industries and scenarios ([NEFI Pathway to Industrial Decarbonisation](#) and [transform.industry - in German](#)).

1. Flexibility – Current developments and trends

The transition to renewable energy and the improvement of energy efficiency are key prerequisites for achieving European and national climate goals. In Austria, this is closely linked to the goal of **climate neutrality by 2040**, which is supported by legal frameworks such as the European Green Deal (“climate-neutral continent by 2050”) and the Renewable Energy Expansion Act (EAG). The integration of renewable, often volatile energy sources poses major challenges for Austria’s manufacturing and energy-intensive industries. To ensure the stability of the energy supply, flexibilities must be identified and implemented. At the same time, technologies for climate neutrality, energy efficiency, and electrification are coming into focus, as they play a crucial role in driving the energy transition and achieving climate targets.

Key trends in flexibility are:

- (1) Energy and gas crisis:** The global pandemic in 2020 and the geopolitical events since 2022 have revealed the profound impact on Europe’s energy and gas markets, highlighting the fragility of market systems. The sharp rise in energy prices and increasing price fluctuations (spreads) influence investment and technology decisions, for example, in favor of heat pumps. Additionally, flexibility options are becoming more attractive, and energy and resource efficiency are playing a greater role. At the same time, geopolitical challenges have intensified national efforts to reduce dependencies on energy imports, particularly gas.
- (2) Electrification:** The electrification of industry involves converting industrial processes and upstream energy supply chains to renewable electricity as the primary energy source. The goal is to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions attributed to the industrial sector. Electrification based on renewable sources plays a key role in reducing emissions. At the same time, it enables the integration of new technologies that can identify and utilise previously untapped flexibility options.
- (3) Digitalisation:** The identification, utilisation, and commercialisation of flexibility potentials increasingly require data-driven processes in industry. Digitalisation and automation are therefore essential aspects that must be considered for the efficient activation and management of flexibilities.
- (4) Pools:** The commercialisation of flexibilities in the form of pools is gaining importance. The following aspects play a key role:
 - Digitalisation and automation facilitate the identification and utilisation of flexibilities.
 - Commercialisation of flexibilities as a pool: Initial approaches already exist; however, the standardisation of interfaces remains an open issue.

2. High-Potential Technologies and Innovations in Flexibility

Based on the general trends in the field of flexibility, the following high-potential technologies and innovations can be identified:

- (1) Simulation and optimisation methods** are crucial for identifying and quantifying flexibility potentials. The focus is particularly on design and operational optimisation methods, as well as their robustness. Relevant approaches include mathematical and empirical methods, as well as artificial intelligence techniques for:
 - Data-driven energy system analysis
 - Data processing
 - Forecasting of energy demand, energy supply, and prices
 - Estimating the impact of technologies on industrial energy systems
 - Detailed temporal resolution and analysis of specific processes
 - Optimising operational strategies to ensure optimal resource use while minimising emissions and/or costs
- (2) Technologies for data collection, processing, and analysis:** Key technologies include energy and data management systems, process control systems, sensor technology, as well as control and regulation technologies.
- (3) All climate neutrality technologies also drive flexibility**, including storage technologies (electrical storage, material storage, steam storage, heat storage), heat pumps, and PtX (Power-to-X) technologies.

However, challenges remain, such as legal frameworks—particularly liability issues related to interventions in existing control systems—as well as concerns regarding data security.

3. Main Research Questions in the field of Flexibility

As part of the NEFI Innovation Hub Flexibility, projects will be developed to address key **technological and process-related research questions**, such as:

- Identification of feasible demand-side flexibility potentials from the overall industrial system level down to individual processes, leveraging data-driven industrial energy systems
- Development of suitable forecasting models for energy demand and supply
- Development of optimisation methods for demand-side management
- Robust optimisation under uncertainties, both in operational and design optimisation
- Flexible and efficient scheduling and control, such as unit commitment and peak shaving
- Integration of storage technologies
- Enhanced coupling of energy carriers and sectors, taking into account a significant share of heat
- Grid- and system-friendly use of industrial demand-side flexibility
- Techno-economic assessment of flexibilities
- Development of industrial load and generation profiles through the integration of climate neutrality technologies

The challenge in answering these questions lies in the identification of feasible flexibility potentials, the forecasting of market prices, and the unlocking of flexibility potentials in the ongoing process (operational optimisation). The increasing share of renewable energy sources urgently requires flexibilities that must be identified and implemented. A prerequisite for the success of these projects is the demonstration and realisation of flexibility potentials while considering ongoing industrial processes.

Relevant **grid- and market-related topics** include:

- Industry-Market-Dashboard
- Grid capacity at transmission and distribution levels, particularly industrial transmission grid connections (Redispatch platform)
- Price forecasting, considering climate targets and other relevant factors
- Analysis of flexibility provision costs at market and grid levels
- New pricing models for flexibility, including time-variable tariffs across sectors
- Asset pooling, including interface development and business models (especially multi-actor coordination and design optimisation)
- Sector coupling and infrastructure development, such as H₂, CO₂, and green gas networks, including storage options and associated price developments

4. Out-of-Scope Topics and Collaborative Overlaps

The following topics and industries are outside the focus area of the Innovation Hub:

- Detailed infrastructure planning: Although the results of this planning are highly relevant, it is not addressed within the scope of this Innovation Hub.
- Process development: The focus is not on the development of specific processes, but on the framework conditions, technology parameters, and the flexible integration of existing processes.

Through cooperation and alignment between the NEFI Innovation Hubs, synergies can be leveraged, technological trends identified, and innovations accelerated.

The NEFI Innovation Hub for Flexibility expects overlaps with the following NEFI Innovation Hubs:

- Industrial Symbiosis: Sector coupling and energy carrier coupling provide flexibility potentials.
- Electrification & Energy Efficiency: Process optimisation and climate neutrality technologies can impact flexibility and efficiency.
- CCUS: Particularly concerning infrastructure development and price trends.
- CO₂-neutral Gases & H₂: Especially regarding infrastructure development, price trends, PtX plants as a flexibility option, and in terms of sector coupling or energy carrier coupling.

5. Hub Co-Leads & Contact Persons

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